

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY IN CITIZEN UPBRINGING

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Abstract

The article analyzes the education in terms of psychology and pedagogy. Besides, it has been noted that the content of education which covers aesthetic, national and moral values should manifest itself in the curriculum. The study was carried out on the basis of different local and foreign scholars', psychologists' views. Azerbaijani proverbs, sayings, bayats, epics, fairy tales, as well as the works of scientists, writers, poets emphasize the national values that enrich the spiritual world of the individual. Pedagogy plays an important role in this case and it influences the learners' psychology, as well. The creation of the content of personality-oriented education is valued as the development of a healthy citizen. This means that in modern conditions, the correct definition of the content of personality-oriented education is understood as a factor that allows to cultivate healthy citizens who are useful to the motherland, people, state and nation.

Keywords: person-oriented education, moral values, citizen, upbringing, personality, pedagogy, psychology

In the pedagogical literature of the Soviet education system, although the problem of the content of personality-oriented education does not find its required interpretation, there are those who briefly touch on the concepts of personality formation. According to Soviet educators, bourgeois psychologists, for example, refer to people who have private property or have a high position. Such people are no longer considered to be individuals when they lose their wealth or are deprived of a high position [7, p. 24]. However, most psychologists, educators, and teachers are of the opinion that identity is not determined by wealth or position. Personality formation applies not only to the adult generation, but also to children and students. For example, both the child and the student are one person. However, the difference from adults is that the student is a developing personality. When a student's personality-oriented education takes into account the manifestation of the student's active attitude to learning, the activity in which the student voluntarily mobilizes all his forces and skills, fulfills the learning tasks within a specified time with great responsibility and hard work. Thus, in the process of formation of the student's personality, his cognitive activity manifests itself on three levels. The first level of cognitive activity is reproductive-imitative, that is, the activity of imitating and performing tasks. The second level is the seeker-executive activity, which is a relatively high level of student activity. Finally, the third level is creative activity, which is the highest level of cognitive activity of the student, characterized by the student setting himself a task and finding original ways to fulfill it [6, p. 53]. According to experts, the student's cognitive activity in the learning process, but also as a result of the use of the "internal" capabilities of the student, as well as the psychological components of interests and needs, i.e cognitive activity. According to psychologist N.D. Levitov, the psychological components of training are:

1. Creating a positive attitude of the student to learning;

2. Organization of the process of direct acquaintance with the training material;

3. Development of thinking, which is a process of comprehension of the studied material and deepening of the given knowledge;

4. Effective organization of the process of remembering and storing the necessary information. That is, strengthening memory. [4, p. 153].

As can be seen, in the acquisition of knowledge, the development of thinking and memory, which is the process of acquaintance and active development of the material studied, is a psychological component of personality formation [6,p. 55].

A positive attitude of the student to learning has a special place in the learning process. The positive attitude of the student to learning should be achieved not by the pressure of adults - teachers, parents, but by his positive, interesting approach to the learning process. However, this does not mean that students' positive attitude towards learning develops spontaneously. Special pedagogical methods should be used for this purpose. Advanced teachers make extensive use of modern learning technologies to develop students' cognitive interest.

For example, M.M Mehdizadeh writes in his book "Ways to improve the educational process in secondary schools": "Ensuring that each student works hard in the classroom, and above all, activating their cognitive activity is one of the main requirements for improving the lesson" [6,p. 279].

We think that academician M.M Mehdizadeh is right, because the development of students' cognitive activity in the pedagogical process is one of the prerequisites for their formation as individuals and as citizens. Such approaches of the scientist should be considered as universal values of education. Because these ideas of Mehdizadeh are considered important for the formation of personality and civic education in the educational process of the international environment.

The views of other pedagogical scientists of Azerbaijan on this issue go beyond the limits of national pedagogical values and rise to the level of universal pedagogical values. One of such pedagogues is Nureddin Kazimov. Nureddin Kazimov's scientific articles on personality development have been used in Russia, Ukraine, Belarus and the Central Asian Republics.

In the article entitled "The role of the pedagogical process in the formation of personality", the professor N.M. Kazimov notes that while studying at school, a student must come to the conclusion that not only to earn a living, get a high salary, pay off parental debt, but also to win the sympathy of the people, to serve the people, to prove that they are useful to the people. The school that forms such a consciousness in students and prepares them for life and work fulfills its mission. This requirement should be taken into account when assessing the performance of the school and the effectiveness of schooling [3,p. 72].

We can evaluate these ideas of Professor Nureddin Kazimov as universal ideas. Because his ideas can be used in other countries of the world in the formation of personality and civic education. Professor Nureddin Kazimov writes in his book "Some Ways to Improve the Quality of Teaching".

In the above-mentioned examples, the authors have made it an important condition for students to be intellectually active in the classroom in order to improve the quality of the lesson. Because the formation of students as a person depends on the quality of knowledge, skills and habits acquired in school and the ability to apply them in life.

All the policy documents prepared in our country since the first years of independence contain rich ideas, relevant provisions and commendable recommendations for the development of students' knowledge and skills and respect for our national values. There are many such ideas, provisions and recommendations in the directive documents on the Education Reform implemented in our country. These ideas, provisions and recommendations imply the implementation of personality-oriented education through the teaching of our national values in the pedagogical process.

By bringing the representatives of the younger generation closer to the national color, acquainting them with our national traditions, constantly informing them about the scientific and pedagogical ideas of our classics, the formation of a real personality - a citizen is in front of pedagogical workers. is one of the most important positions. Ways to solve these problems are determined by our valuable pedagogues, psychologists and teachers, special attention is paid to the in-depth study of our pedagogical history.

The culture of behavior of each nation in accordance with national and moral values stems from its national upbringing. The attitude of each nation to the homeland, the children of the homeland, the borders of the homeland, its territorial integrity, its ecological environment, national customs and human traditions are completely different from each other. Let's express our opinion with a practical example. For example, boards were hung in the alpine meadows to protect plants and flowers. It is written in French: "Enjoy these beautiful

flowers, but why do you break them?" It is written in English: "Please do not cut the flowers." For the Germans, this is no longer a request, but a prohibition: "It is forbidden to cut flowers!" Without comment, we would like to ask: Couldn't all these boards be written in the same context? Why is each of them written differently in the language of a different people, and is there a special reason for this? Yes, there is a special reason why the boards are written in different contexts, and that is because there are national values that belong to each nation separately. The feeling of love for the people, the homeland, the national traditions is formed differently in different nations.

Azerbaijani proverbs, sayings, bayats, epics, fairy tales, as well as the works of scientists, writers, poets emphasize the national values that enrich the spiritual world of the individual. All the national values that a person proudly refers to are based on national values. The fact that each of the proverbs has an educative and instructive character also substantiates the correctness of our opinion. In the parables, the person in front is warned and admonished. In this case, it is recommended that the person be intelligent, moral, and sympathetic to science and scientists. If some of the bayats are dedicated to the motherland, the land, love for each other, children, parents, family, some to be scientific, to acquire knowledge, and some to purify the moral and spiritual image of people, especially the rising generation. dedicated to the resurrection. Thus, national values are a key factor in ensuring the comprehensive development of the individual.

Our great leader Heydar Aliyev said at the First Youth Forum: "Our youth must be educated in the national spirit, on the basis of our national and moral values. Our youth must know our history, our past, our language, our national values. It is impossible to be a young patriot who does not know our national values, national traditions and history well. Every young person should be a patriot. Patriotism is a great concept ... To be loyal to the Motherland, to love the Motherland, to be attached to the land - this is patriotism" [1,p. 160].

Babayev Javid underlines the significance of aesthetic values in education, particularly in language learning: "Furthermore, person-oriented content of education includes aesthetic values as music, painting and literature which are already the constituent of the curriculum" [2, p.130].

The ideas of our national leader to instill national values and feelings of patriotism in growing teenagers and young people were emphasized in several reports and speeches during the Soviet era. At that time, there were educators who agreed with and defended such ideas of HA Aliyev. Or there were scholars who expressed independent views on national values. For example, academic M.A. Noting the role of national schools in the former USSR, Prokofiev wrote: "We are not Ivans who do not understand kinship. National schools are an important educational institution for internationalists. A person separated from his national roots risks becoming a cosmopolitan. There are many good teachers in the national schools of the country" [8,p.12].

Doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor, full member of the Academy of Pedagogical and Social Sciences, honored teacher of the republic Zahid Garalov considered it impossible to give a large textbook "Semya" to the Republican schools, which is far from the content of national education and filled with facts not specific to Azerbaijani families. It is noteworthy that the Republican leadership has also decided to develop an independent program and textbook, methodical literature for secondary schools in this direction [6, p.78]. All this proves that it is very important to cultivate a personality based on national pedagogical values. However, the understanding of national pedagogical values has a stronger effect when they are compared with universal pedagogical values. Educated, educated, enter a more serious stage of personality-oriented development in the context of comparing national pedagogical values with the national pedagogical values of the peoples of Europe.

Because it is possible to differentiate the richness, integrity, educational significance, moral and spiritual qualities of the national pedagogical values of Azerbaijan in comparison with the pedagogical values of foreign countries. It is in the process of differentiation that a wide range of opportunities opens up for the formation of the student's personality and civic education. In conclusion, we can say that by studying the possibilities of educating citizens with a person-centered approach in terms of international experience, it is possible to take successful steps in this area. Professor Nureddin Kazimov explains the essence of the category of education in the book "School Pedagogy" as follows: education - as an integral part of socio-economic life, purposeful, planned and organized learning in relevant educational institutions for a certain period of time, otherwise the result is a set of systematized knowledge, skills and habits, as well as moral qualities [4, p. 104].

Professor Nureddin Kazimov answers the question of what are the main features of general secondary education as follows: generality, unity, labor orientation, polytechnic character, reference to national values, taking into account abilities are the main features of general secondary education [4, p. 106]. The views of the esteemed professor on the main features of secondary education are both valuable and relevant. The idea of referring to national values is more relevant. The idea of taking into account the abilities of the professor is a factor that emphasizes the implementation of personality-oriented education. It is a well-known fact that people are different in appearance, temperament, character, abilities, and so on. therefore, they do not resemble each other. Speaking of abilities, it should be noted that most scholars who conduct research on the problem of personality-oriented education, who speak about the formation of personality, prefer the discovery and development of abilities in the formation of student personality. Such an approach should be considered one of the modern approaches.

Professor F. Sadigov, who conducts research on the identification and development of abilities to increase the level of personality of students, assessed the formation of children's artistic creativity as factors influencing the formation of their personality. Because

the formation of students' artistic creativity, along with their level of imagination, also increases their ability to think. Systematic work on the formation of students' creative abilities helps students to identify relevant aspects of talent. In other words, the discovery of students' abilities is valued as an in-depth study of their natural abilities.

In psychology, the concept of "natural possibilities" includes not only the anatomical and physiological features of the organism, but also the psychophysiological properties, and interprets these results as a key aspect. Psychophysiological properties are, first of all, the subtle sensitivity to color, visual memory, sensitivity to music, etc., which manifests itself in children in the very early stages of acquisition, and sometimes in adults who do not engage in certain activities on a regular basis. such properties are understood. Such natural possibilities manifest themselves when a person comes in contact with a certain irritating object, which to one degree or another advocates them. For example, music, scenery, etc. High emotional sensitivity and propensity for this activity are clearly seen in children with appropriate natural abilities during perception [3, p. 426].

Children's natural abilities later influence their development as individuals. Sometimes families do not pay attention to the natural opportunities of children. In many cases, in the pedagogical process, subject teachers, leaders of artistic circles manage to reveal the natural potential of children. Proper identification of natural opportunities should be considered as a key criterion for the development of the student's future activities.

The problem of talent has a special place among the current problems of modern psychology. This is, first of all, due to the fact that the analysis of the interaction of abilities in the process of activity is not only a scientific and theoretical issue. It has great practical significance.

Talent is a self-sufficient union of abilities, which is a condition for the successful performance of one or more activities.

If various abilities such as observation, poetic vision, image, memory of feelings and movements, creative imagination, figurative thinking, richness of vocabulary and expressive language, richness of word associations are organically combined in literary activity, it is a literary talent. The same words apply to other types of talent. [3, p. 431].

In many cases, parents involve their children in specialties based on their own desires (meaning the wishes of the parents - M.E.), without taking into account the natural capabilities, abilities and talents of their children. At the same time, these children are forced to distance themselves from education, realizing that the specialties they are studying contradict their natural abilities. One of the prominent composers of Azerbaijan, the world-famous Gara Garayev, was directed by his parents to medical education. In other words, Gara Garayev's father, Abulfaz Garayev, encourages him to study at Gara Medical University, where he completed his secondary education, without taking into account his natural abilities. Kara's interest, inclination and desire was to become a composer. That

is, his natural abilities were manifested in the high artistic abilities. That is why he left his studies at the Black Medical University and fled to Moscow, where he successfully passed an exam and was admitted to the composition department of the Conservatory. Gara Garayev, who became a composer in the class of the famous Russian composer Shostakovich, became famous as a world-famous composer. In other words, Gara Garayev is becoming one of the most prominent personalities in the world because of his natural resources. So, one of the modern approaches is to take into account the ability to create the content of personality-oriented education.

We think that it is possible to determine which of the above-mentioned abilities of the students we train in the pedagogical process are more inclined. That is, by using the personality-oriented content of education, taking into account and motivating the interests of learners, we can cultivate a future person who will be competitive in the future, with the ability to apply the acquired knowledge and independent creative thinking. The students we educate and bring up, regardless of their abilities, must be patriots who protect and develop national moral and universal values, be loyal to the ideas of Azerbaijanism, be independent and creative thinkers and citizens.

In conclusion, we must say that in modern approaches, the creation of the content of personality-oriented education is valued as the development of a healthy citizen. This means that in modern conditions,

the correct definition of the content of personality-oriented education is understood as a factor that allows to cultivate healthy citizens who are useful to the motherland, people, state and nation. Taking into account these factors is one of the most important criteria for the education of educated and personality-oriented citizens.

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